

CoARA

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Università di Camerino

CoARA ACTION PLAN

2024-2027

Università di Camerino

CoARA working group
coordinated by prof. Anna Maria Eleuteri

Lorenzo Di Nello
Emanuela Laliscia
Melissa Mancini
Francesca Pompei
Roberto Spurio
Angela Trapananti

CoARA Action Plan
approved by the Academic Governing Bodies
on July 24th, 2024

The University of Camerino (UNICAM) joined, in 2022, CoARA, the Coalition for Advancing of Research Evaluation, promoted at European level and, later, the Italian National Chapter, a network of 45 Italian organizations, including AN-VUR, which intends to promote and to implement the CoARA principles.

The main activities of the national working group are aimed at:

- a. Proposing actions to support the implementation of the 10 fundamental commitments (Commitments) that constitute the CoARA Mission;
- b. Promoting bi-directional relations with the Working Groups operating at European level, with the aim of comparing proposals and results;
- c. Establishing a reasonable and actionable roadmap to implement CoARA principles and commitments in the 2024-2027 timeframe.

The joining to the CoARA National Chapter has been realized through the signature of the document ARRA (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment), containing all the fundamental principles of CoARA, the priorities to be pursued and a series of general proposals for the implementation of good practices for the evaluation of research institutions, research projects and researchers. The ARRA document also examines into details the 10 key Commitments of CoARA, defining, for each one, the objective and the scope together with a reform path for their implementation.

The ARRA document aims at conveying a twofold message: that evaluation should recognise the diversity of research contributions and career paths in research, taking into account the specific nature of the different disciplines, and that each institution should take responsibility, with the available tools but also with new procedures to be implemented, to promote good evaluation practices, giving maximum value to the quality and impact of research, without ever derogating from the principles of methodological rigour, reproducibility and integrity.

By joining the CoARA National Chapter, UNICAM is committed to implementing systemic actions, capable of contributing to a path of cultural change that modifies the current evaluation system based almost exclusively on quantitative metrics. The weakness of these quantifiable indicators stems from the fact that “Bibliometric indicators tell a story, but not the whole story” (Dutch Research Council, 2019, p. 4). In fact, in order to highlight the variety and the heterogeneity of academic activities, experiences and skills, it is essential to develop guidelines and procedures leading to the redefinition of research evaluation principles and methods that take into account qualitative aspects in a fair and transparent manner. In this way, all members of the academic community will be able to know the criteria adopted for the evaluation of the research and how they are applied.

Such changes, for which the quality and impact of research and researchers will be assessed based on more appropriate criteria and processes, will also include the acknowledging of the Open Science practices adopted. Recently, UNICAM has developed an Open Science Policy to encourage and support researchers to conduct their research in accordance with the principles of Open Science.

In order to maintain the commitment made in 2005 with the signing of the European Charter for Researchers, UNICAM continues its path of implementation of the principles set out in the Charter as well as in the principles included in the New European Charter. In particular, in the Pillar 2 on responsible evaluation of research and researchers (Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe - Annex 2).

The main challenges that UNICAM intends to address are:

- i) **communication** and awareness raising of the CoARA principles by the whole academic community;
- ii) the **connection** between the different Areas of the University and the Schools, essential to carry out a critical analysis of the processes and evaluation criteria, aimed at the regular review and improvement of practices, also with the support of experts outside UNICAM;
- iii) **cooperation** and **exchange** of information and procedures with other research organisations and evaluation agencies, in order to optimally respond to the challenges that the research evaluation reform process will pose in the near future.

Considering the guidelines proposed by CoARA and the complexity of Academic institutions, which are aware of the cultural and structural changes that such a reform entails, through this Action Plan, the University identifies a series of procedures and actions to be implemented in order to redefine the institutional processes of evaluation of research and researchers. The importance recognized to these aspects is demonstrated by the fact that they represent one of the macro-objectives outlined in the University's Strategic Plan 2024-2029.

The activities of the action plan are classified according to the expected implementation time, short and long term. For each activity, systematically linked to the relevant CoARA commitments, timeframes and implementation managers shall be indicated, together with objectively measurable indicators to monitor implementation status over time.

A	ACTIONS IN THE SHORT TERM (UP TO THE END OF 2024)	RELATED COARA COMMITMENTS	TIMEFRAME/ TARGET	RESPONSIBILITY	INDICATORS
1	To give visibility to the research evaluation reform process, dedicating a specific section on the University's website that collects the main CoARA documents, the action plan that UNICAM intends to adopt and any other documents and/or instruments that the University will implement so as to make them available for consultation and analysis in an open manner both by internal and external actors to UNICAM, encouraging sharing with a view to facilitating collective progress towards CoARA.	7, 9	Last trimester 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delegate for the implementation of university policies for the European Research Area - IT Center 	Online publication of the new web page, dedicated to CoARA
2	To actively participation in the Working Groups (WG) of CoARA - National Chapter.	8	Last trimester 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vice Rector for Research and Technology Transfer - Delegate for the implementation of university policies for the European Research Area 	No. 1 formal participation at least one WG
3	To promote the appropriate use of quantitative parameters in the evaluation of research, focusing on qualitative aspects (giving a central to the peer review process) discouraging the inappropriate use of quantitative indicators. To discourage the use of international rankings in the evaluation of research institutions.	3, 4	Last trimester 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University Research Board - Committee for Quality Management of Human Resources for Research 	No. 1 Position Paper signed by the University Governance

B	ACTIONS IN THE MID & LONG TERM (UP TO THE END OF 2026)	RELATED COARA COMMITMENTS	TIMEFRAME/ TARGET	RESPONSIBILITY	INDICATORS
1	To involve all the University Schools in the processes of analysis of current practices and in the improvement of research evaluation procedures according to the principles and guidelines of CoARA.	6	Last trimester 2025	University Research Board	Publication of No. 1 document containing information on each school
2	To include in the Evaluation System of Researchers' Performance (ESRP) the following activities: a) the work carried out by UNICAM researchers as "peer reviewers" (in relation to scientific publications and research projects) which can be defined as the zero of the critical evaluation process of scientific production; b) revision of the doctoral thesis; c) participation in national and international doctoral commissions; d) recognised participation in editorial boards (e.g. scientific journal editor).	1, 2, 6	First semester 2025 elaboration of a proposal for integration to the Competent University Bodies. Second half of 2025 , activation of the approved integration measures.	- Committee for Quality Management of Human Resources for Research - Educational Planning and Quality System Unit	No. 1 proposal shared with the competent University Bodies
3	To disseminate CoARA principles to the university community through the involvement of CoARA European Steering Committee members in order to present the state of the art of the research evaluation reform and to discuss the integration of CoARA principles in the Italian research evaluation system.	9, 7	First trimester 2026	- Committee for Quality Management of Human Resources for Research - Vice Rector for Research and Technology Transfer - Delegate for the implementation of university policies for the European Research Area - Delegate for Research Quality Assessment and Assurance (VQR)	No. 1 public event
4	To monitor the overall editorial activity of each School, through the periodic analysis of the scientific production of the Schools and the production of reports that take into account both the aggregated data of the Schools and the trends of development of specific areas of research, in bibliometric and non-bibliometric fields.	3	First trimester 2025	- Schools Research Boards - Libraries and Higher Education area	Production of the first monitoring report to be integrated into the University/ School research review report shared with the relevant bodies of the University
5	To promote e-tools such as "Think Check Submit", to help researchers identify the most appropriate journals where they can publish the scientific data produced, and to provide a wide-range overview of issues related to publications (licensing, copyright, long-term archiving, predatory journals).	7	First trimester 2025	- Libraries and Higher Education area	No. 1 event to present and launch at least one IT tool to the UNICAM academic community

6	<p>To identify (assignment or recruitment) a new professional with the following responsibilities:</p> <p>a) linking the areas (Research, Personnel, SAS-Libraries, Quality Systems) and the University Schools to improve the transparent collection and processing of data on research evaluation practices;</p> <p>b) organisation and management of a technical infrastructure making research data available in accordance with FAIR principles;</p> <p>c) interaction with the Knowledge Transfer Manager.</p>	5	<p>First semester of 2025 elaboration of a formal proposal by the FPQRU</p> <p>Last semester 2025 assignment/recruitment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delegate for the implementation of university policies for the European Research Area - Directorate General 	<p>No. 1 formal assignment/recruitment document</p>
7	<p>To elaborate guidelines useful for narrative CV writing and adoption, in recruitment procedures, of the narrative CV as a tool for evaluating research with the aim to avoid focussing only on bibliometric indicators.</p>	10	<p>Last trimester 2025 (narrative cv guidelines)</p> <p>First semester 2026 introduction in recruitment procedures of the demand for narrative CV.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Committee for Quality Management of Human Resources for Research - Human Resources for Research - Human Resources Unit - Research and Technology Transfer Unit 	<p>No. 1 publication of guidelines</p> <p>No. 1 document of approval of the competent governing bodies about the introduction of the narrative CV in recruitment procedures</p>
8	<p>To include in the calls for recruitment the indication of the UNICAM subscription to CoARA, highlighting the adherence to CoARA commitments in the evaluation procedure.</p>	9	<p>Last trimester 2026</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University Research Board - Human Resources Unit - Directorate General 	<p>No. 1 DG provision</p>
9	<p>To provide an annual update/revision of this action plan, taking into account also the contribution deriving from the participation in CoARA international forums during the year.</p>	9	<p>First semester 2025</p> <p>First semester 2026</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Committee for Quality Management of Human Resources for Research 	<p>No. 1 annual meeting on document update/revision</p>

